

Spatio-temporal modeling and simulation of a mode-locked tapered semiconductor diode laser

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Abstract. We present a theoretical model and numerical simulation results of the dynamics of a monolithic edge-emitting mode-locked tapered quantum well laser. The comprehensive simulation employs a $(2 + 1)$ dimensional traveling wave model and incorporates models for lateral current spreading and carrier diffusion, while also addressing thermal effects in the laser cavity. Our investigation of the pulse generation by passive mode locking demonstrates good agreement with experimental observations. Furthermore, we perform a study of the intra-cavity propagation dynamics of the laser, which provides valuable insights for a better understanding of the laser's behavior.

Keywords: diode laser, tapered laser, passive mode locking, traveling wave model, simulation

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1. Introduction

Mode-locking (ML) is a well-established technique for generating picosecond or femtosecond optical pulses using lasers [1]. In recent years, edge-emitting mode-locked diode lasers (MLDLs) have gained attention as a promising alternative to traditional solid-state lasers, such as Ti:sapphire lasers. MLDLs offer significant advantages in terms of cost, operational simplicity, and wavelength versatility, making them appealing for a broad range of research and industrial applications.

Passive mode locking can be achieved monolithically in diode lasers by electrically separating the laser cavity into at least two sections: a long gain section operated under forward bias and a short saturable absorber section under reverse bias [2]. The compactness and robustness of these diode lasers make them ideal for integration into miniaturized and portable systems. For instance, MLDLs have been demonstrated as pulse sources in terahertz time-domain spectroscopy [3, 4], and in compact two-photon polymerization systems [5, 6].

One disadvantage of MLDLs is that the typical pulse length of several picoseconds is often longer than desired. Moreover, the peak power in the watt range is insufficient for certain applications. The strong chirp characteristic of pulses emitted by MLDLs allows them to be easily compressed into the sub-picosecond range [7]. This compression shortens the pulse duration, increasing peak power, but it comes at the expense of added system complexity. One effective approach to address the issue of low peak power is to integrate flared gain regions in the laser cavity, as found in tapered lasers. This design can significantly boost the peak power output [8, 9, 10, 11].

For a comprehensive understanding of MLDL dynamics, simulations of these devices are essential. Various simulation approaches are available [12], each offering a different level of complexity along with their own strengths and limitations. The simplest approach is through time-domain lumped models [1], but their utility for MLDLs is restricted by assumptions about pulse saturation and minimal gain and loss per round trip. Delayed differential equation (DDE) models [13] provide valuable qualitative insights and, in simpler cases, quantitative predictions. However, their reliability and accuracy are limited when it comes to more realistic complex multi-section laser designs. The most precise method for simulating MLDLs is the traveling wave model (TWM), which treats both axial position and time on an equal footing [14]. However, this accuracy comes at the expense of high computational demands.

While previous theoretical and numerical studies on MLDLs have mostly focused on straight waveguide configurations, there are relatively few studies addressing the simulation of tapered MLDLs. A comparative study between straight and tapered waveguide MLDLs was reported using a modified DDE model [15]. Tapered MLDLs have also been simulated with TWM in $(1 + 1)D$, covering longitudinal and temporal dimensions, while considering the partial dependence of certain parameters on the lateral waveguide width [16, 10]. However, an accurate simulation of pulse propagation and amplification in flared gain regions requires fully accounting for variations in the lateral

structure along the cavity, necessitating a complete 2D (lateral + longitudinal) spatial model. Another significant challenge specific to tapered MLDLs is the pronounced self-heating observed in the flared gain region, which requires solving the heat-flow equation in addition to the traveling-wave equations for optical fields and carrier densities.

In this article, we present an advanced numerical analysis of the optical behavior of a tapered MLDL using a (2 + 1)D TWM that fully incorporates the lateral, longitudinal and temporal dimensions. This allows the simulation of longitudinally varying lateral structures such as tapered lasers and amplifiers [17]. Furthermore, our simulation includes a detailed description of carrier transport within the laser’s lateral-vertical domain, an aspect often overlooked in previous theoretical studies on MLDLs. This carrier transport model accounts for lateral current spreading outside the contact stripe, carrier diffusion, and spatial hole burning. As a result, our simulation enables the study of phenomena such as carrier induced anti-index guiding, self-focusing and filamentation, which are commonly observed in broad-area lasers. Additionally, our simulation integrates a stationary thermal model for the lateral-longitudinal temperature distribution, which is interactively coupled with the optical and carrier transport models by modifying thermally dependent parameters. This thermal model describes the heat accumulation and flow within the laser, providing insights into self-heating effects, such as the thermally induced lensing phenomena.

This paper is structured as follows: First, we introduce the laser under investigation, along with a brief summary of the experimental results. Second, we provide an in-depth description of the simulation tool and its three theoretical models. Next, we present the specific device model for a tapered MLDL and its associated parameters within the simulation framework. This is followed by a detailed discussion of the simulation results, including both the electro-optical performance and additional insights into the intra-cavity dynamics.

2. Device design and experimental results

The laser structure under investigation comprises a gain-guided tapered (TP) gain section, an index-guided ridge waveguide (RW) gain section and a short RW section serving as saturable absorber, see figure 1. Details of the laser design are given in table 1. The layer stack consists of an AlGaAs based waveguide with a 4.8 μm thick waveguide core and compressively strained InGaAsP double quantum wells (QW), with each QW having a thickness of 6 nm. Lateral electro-optical confinement is achieved in the RW sections by the ridge, defined by trenches etched into the p-side of the layer stack, with a p-contact on top. In the TP section, electrical confinement is achieved by a shallow implantation of the region outside of the p-contact area. Despite having the same epitaxial structure throughout, each section can be electrically controlled independently. For simplicity, the RW and TP gain sections were shorted and driven by a single current source providing a gain current I , while the saturable absorber section, located at the high-reflection-coated rear facet, was operated under a reverse bias U applied by a

voltage source. The laser is soldered epi-side up onto a CuW submount. A second CuW submount is soldered on top of the TP section to improve the heat spreading. The whole assembly is then soldered onto a C-mount package and placed on a heat sink maintained at 25 °C. In the following, we present a selection of results from the experimental characterization of the device. A detailed description of the experimental setup and a thorough discussion of the measurement outcomes can be found in our previous paper [8].

Figure 1. Schematic sketch of the tapered MLDL under study.

Table 1. Design parameters of the tapered MLDL under study.

parameter	value	unit
total cavity length	6000	μm
length of TP section	3800	μm
full flare angle of TP section	4	$^\circ$
length of RW gain section	2000	μm
length of RW saturable absorber	200	μm
ridge width	5	μm
width of trenches (either side)	20	μm
front/rear facet reflectivity	0.01/0.98	

Figure 2 shows the dependence of averaged output power, pulse width τ_p , and peak power on the gain current I for a reverse bias voltage of $U = 1.5$ V, along with an exemplary auto-correlation function (ACF) trace for a gain current of 3.3 A. The pulse width was determined from the full width at half maximum (FWHM) τ_{ACF} of the Gaussian fit to the ACF as $\tau_p = 0.707\tau_{\text{ACF}}$ [18]. This pulse width, together with the repetition frequency of 6.3 GHz (corresponding to a period of 160 ps), was used to calculate the peak power from the average output power.

The laser turns on at approximately $I = 2.5$ A and emits an average power of about 1.5 W at $I = 4.5$ A. Within the current range of 2.9 A to 3.8 A, the laser operates in a fundamental ML regime, as confirmed by the mapping of the radio frequency (RF)

Figure 2. Experimental results at $U = 1.5$ V: Averaged output power (left, black solid line), pulse width determined from the FWHM of the Gaussian fit of the measured ACF (middle, blue solid line, left axis) and the corresponding peak power (middle, orange dashed line, right axis) versus gain current, and the ACF trace (right, red solid line) with its Gaussian fit (right, red dotted line) at a gain current of $I = 3.3$ A.

Figure 3. Experimental results at $U = 1.5$ V: Pseudo-color mapping of the normalized RF power (top) and the optical power (bottom) against the gain current.

power spectrum (see figure 3). Within this ML region, the pulse width slightly widens from 3.5 ps to 4.7 ps, and the peak power rises from 23 W to 35 W with increasing gain current. Figure 3 illustrates pseudo-color mappings of the RF and optical power as a function of the gain current. The stable ML range is observed between 2.9 A and 3.8 A. This range is characterized by a sharp RF peak at 6.3 GHz and its harmonics, along with a distinct optical spectrum with a FWHM of about 1 nm (3-dB width) centered around 831 nm, persisting up to approximately 3.8 A. Further measurement results are discussed in Section 4, where they are compared with simulation results.

3. Theoretical models and simulation tool

The varying lateral structure along the laser cavity necessitates consideration of both lateral (x) and longitudinal (z) variations in light propagation. Although it can be assumed that the optical mode remains invariant in the vertical (y) dimension due to the predefined epitaxial structure, the y -axis plays a crucial role in injection current spreading and heat flow. Therefore, an accurate simulation must therefore encompass these vertical, lateral, and longitudinal complexities, accounting for the dynamic interplay among optical behavior, electro-thermal effects, and structural variations within the device. An appropriate theoretical model was derived from Maxwell's and drift-diffusion equations in [19] to describe the spatio-temporal behavior of continuous-wave (CW) operated or pulsed driven semiconductor lasers and amplifiers [20, 21]. In this section, we summarize the basic model equations and discuss the specific considerations for simulating MLDLs.

3.1. Optical model

Assuming minimal alteration of the fundamental vertical mode within the laser cavity and separating the rapid variations of the optical field with respect to time t and axial position z , the slowly varying forward- and backward-propagating envelopes $u^\pm(x, z, t)$ of the optical field obey the traveling wave equations

$$\left[\frac{n_g}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \pm \frac{\partial}{\partial z} + \frac{i}{2\bar{n}k_0} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \right] u^\pm = - [i\Delta\beta^\pm + \mathcal{D}] u^\pm + f_{\text{sp}}^\pm, \quad (1)$$

where c is the speed of light in vacuum, $k_0 = 2\pi/\lambda$ with λ being the reference vacuum wavelength, n_g and \bar{n} are effective group and reference phase index, respectively. \mathcal{D} is an operator representing the Lorentzian dispersion of the optical gain [22, 23] and the stochastic terms f_{sp}^\pm describe the spontaneous emission [24].

The output power at the front facet at $z = L$ with a reflectivity r_f is given by

$$P = (1 - |r_f|^2) \frac{\hbar\omega dc}{n_g} \int |u^\pm(x, L)|^2 dx, \quad (2)$$

where d is the thickness of active layer.

The complex relative propagation factor $\Delta\beta$ reads

$$\Delta\beta^\pm = k_0\Delta n_0 + k_0\Delta n_N + k_0\Delta n_T + k_0\Delta n_{2P}^\pm + \frac{i}{2} (g - \alpha_0 - \alpha_N - \alpha_{2P}^\pm). \quad (3)$$

The first term on the right-hand side of (3) accounts for a deviation of the effective index from the reference effective index \bar{n} in certain regions. The second and third terms describe the dependence of the effective index on the excess carrier density N

$$\Delta n_N(x, z, N) = -\sqrt{n'_N N} \quad (4)$$

and the temperature T

$$\Delta n_T = n'_T \int [T(x, y, z) - T_{\text{HS}}] |\Phi|^2(y) dy \quad (5)$$

respectively, where n'_N and n'_T are corresponding pre-factors. T_{HS} is the heat sink temperature and $|\Phi|^2$ is the intensity profile of the vertical waveguide mode. The fourth term is due to the Kerr effect (complementary to two-photon absorption),

$$\Delta n_{2\text{P}}^{\pm} = n'_{2\text{P}}(|u^+|^2 + |u^-|^2 + |u^{\mp}|^2) \quad (6)$$

with $n'_{2\text{P}}$ being the pre-factor.

The optical gain is modeled as

$$g = \frac{g' \ln \left(\frac{\max(N, N_0)}{N_{\text{tr}}} \right)}{1 + \epsilon_g(|u^+|^2 + |u^-|^2)} \quad (7)$$

where g' is a pre-factor, N_{tr} is the transparency carrier density, N_0 is the gain clamping carrier density, introduced to remove the singularity for $N \rightarrow 0$, and ϵ_g is the gain compression factor, used to account for effects that are not consistently included in this model, like carrier heating and spectral hole burning. The underlying intra-band dynamics can be neglected as long as the pulses are longer than a few picoseconds [25], which is still just the case here. The differential gain is assumed to be temperature independent. The transparency carrier density varies with temperature as

$$N_{\text{tr}}(T) = N_{\text{tr}}(T_{\text{HS}}) + \partial_T N_{\text{tr}}(T - T_{\text{HS}}). \quad (8)$$

The absorption is comprised of background absorption α_0 , free carrier absorption

$$\alpha_N = f_N N, \quad (9)$$

and two-photon absorption

$$\alpha_{2\text{P}}^{\pm} = f_{2\text{P}}(|u^+|^2 + |u^-|^2 + |u^{\mp}|^2) \quad (10)$$

where f_N and $f_{2\text{P}}$ are corresponding cross sections [22].

For the gain and saturable absorber sections the same model equations and the same set of parameters such as g' , N_{tr} and ϵ_g are used. Note that due to the logarithmic gain model, the differential gain increases with decreasing carrier density, $\partial g / \partial N \propto g' / N$ for $N > N_0$. Therefore, the differential gain is larger in the absorber section than in the gain sections, which is necessary for mode locking [12].

3.2. Electronic model

The electronic model is derived from the drift-diffusion equations assuming a constant quasi-Fermi potential of the electrons (equals zero) in the n-doped region, assuming

local charge neutrality in the active layer, and neglecting recombination outside the active layer [20, 26]. The excess carrier density in the active layer, averaged over y , obeys the equation

$$\frac{\partial N}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(D_{\text{eff}}(N) \frac{\partial N}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{j}{ed} - AN - BN^2 - CN^3 - R_{\text{stim}} \quad (11)$$

with the effective diffusion coefficient

$$D_{\text{eff}}(N) = (p_0 + N) \mu_p \frac{\partial \varphi_F}{\partial N}, \quad (12)$$

and the injection current density

$$j = \sigma_p \frac{\partial \varphi_p}{\partial y}. \quad (13)$$

In equations (11) and (13), e is the elementary charge, A , B and C are recombination parameters, μ_p is the hole mobility, and σ_p and φ_p is the hole conductivity and quasi-Fermi potential in the p-doped layer adjacent to the active layer.

The rate of stimulated recombination is given by

$$R_{\text{stim}} = \frac{c}{n_g} \text{Re} \sum_{\nu=\pm} u^{\nu*} [g - 2\mathcal{D}] u^\nu. \quad (14)$$

The Fermi voltage (difference between quasi-Fermi potentials of holes and electrons) reads

$$\varphi_F = \varphi_p - \varphi_n = \frac{E_g}{e} + \frac{k_B T}{e} \left[F_{1/2}^{-1} \left(\frac{n_0 + N}{N_c} \right) + F_{1/2}^{-1} \left(\frac{p_0 + N}{N_v} \right) \right] \quad (15)$$

where E_g is the energy gap, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, n_0 and p_0 are the equilibrium electron and hole densities, N_c and N_v are the conduction and valence band effective density of states, and $F_{1/2}^{-1}(\cdot)$ denotes the inverse Fermi integral [27].

The quasi-Fermi potential of the holes is obtained by solving the Laplace-equation [28]

$$\nabla_{xy} (\sigma_p \nabla_{xy} \varphi_p) = 0 \quad (16)$$

in the xy -plane at every z mesh point within the p-doped region. At the boundary to the p-contacts of the gain sections, the quasi-Fermi potential equals the applied voltage U_0 ($\varphi_p = U_0$). At the boundary to the active layer the potential corresponds to the Fermi voltage in (15). At all other device boundaries the derivative of the electrochemical potential normal to the device surface vanishes. More details and the temperature dependence of the parameters entering the electronic model can be found in [20].

This current flow model was developed specifically for a forward biased pn junction, where excess carriers are injected into the active layer, as appropriate for the gain regions of the MLDLs. Conversely, in the reverse biased saturable absorber section, excess carriers in the active layer are generated solely optically through the absorption of photons via the stimulated recombination term in (14). In practical terms, when

a reverse bias is applied, electrons are attracted towards the p-contact, while holes migrate towards the n-contact. To model this effect in simulation, the applied voltage to the p-contact of the saturable absorber section is set to zero and the reverse bias effect is accounted for by increasing the recombination parameter A .

3.3. Thermal model

In MLDLs, there are two types of self-heating effects. Firstly, rapid temperature fluctuations occur within the active layer due to the propagation of optical pulses, potentially resulting in varying carrier and lattice temperatures [29]. While this paper does not explicitly model these rapid fluctuations, their impact is effectively considered as gain compression. Secondly, over longer periods, given the high repetition frequency of the pulses, an almost stationary temperature distribution can be achieved. Therefore, in the case of MLDL, it suffices to solve the stationary heat-flow equation

$$-\nabla_{xy} [\kappa_L \nabla_{xy} T] = \langle h \rangle \quad (17)$$

where κ_L is the thermal conductivity of the lattice and $\langle \cdot \rangle$ denotes temporal averaging. The heat flow is only considered in the xy -planes for each mesh point z . The heat-flow equation is solved subject to a Robin boundary condition at the heat sink and vanishing heat flow at all other boundaries.

The heat source density h consists of Joule heat, absorption heat, recombination heat, and quantum defect heat as given in [30]. Due to the limitations of the current flow model the Joule heat is ignored in the saturable absorber section.

To solve (17), an iterative procedure is necessary because the heat source density h is initially unknown. In the initial iteration, the electro-optical model is solved under isothermal conditions with $T = T_{HS}$. The heat source is then calculated accordingly, and the averaged temperature distribution $T(x, y, z)$ is obtained by solving (17). The temperature-dependent parameters are adjusted as necessary and used in the next iteration to obtain new solutions of the electro-optical model. This iterative process continues until a stationary temperature state is achieved. More details on the numerical procedure can be found in [31].

3.4. Device model and simulation parameters

The electro-optical model, as well as the thermal model, presented in the previous section, is implemented in the software “BALaser” jointly developed by Ferdinand-Braun-Institut (FBH) and Weierstrass Institute for Applied Analysis and Stochastics (WIAS) Berlin [32, 33]. Having previously demonstrated the simulation of a slightly tapered RW laser operating in CW mode [34], we now extend this general-purpose simulation tool to address the complex dynamics of strongly tapered MLDLs.

The simulation domain of our MLDL in the xz -plane, shown in figure 4, spans 0.5 mm in width and 6 mm in length, with lateral and longitudinal resolutions of 0.2 μm and 5 μm , respectively. The entire domain is divided into seven distinct regions, labeled

Figure 4. Sketch of the simulation domain in the xz -plane of the tapered MLDL, with seven different regions marked by colors.

M1–M7, depending on their functionality, bias condition, and vertical structure, each characterized by varying simulation parameters. Regions M1, M5, M6 and M7 represent unbiased areas without electrical contacts. In region M7 the background absorption is artificially enhanced to prevent reflections from the lateral simulation boundaries. Regions M2 and M3, which correspond to the TP and RW gain sections, are electrically biased with a voltage U_0 . The TP region is represented by 40 rectangular subregions with gradually varying lateral widths. Regions M4 and M6 correspond to the saturable absorber and its trench, respectively, with a higher A parameter than other regions to simulate the reverse bias effect. In both trench regions M5 and M6, $\Delta n_0 = -\Delta n_{\text{eff}}$ applies, where Δn_{eff} represents the difference between the effective indices of the layer stacks in the ridge and in the trench.

Most of the parameters used in the simulation are standard values commonly found in the literature [35]. Some key parameters are listed in table 2. The effective parameters entering the optical model are weighted by the profile of the vertical waveguide mode [19]. The mode profile, along with the corresponding \bar{n} , n_g , Δn_{eff} , and Γ , are obtained from a one-dimensional mode solver using a refractive index model of AlGaAs published in [36]. The group index, derived from the dispersion of the effective index, agrees well with the value obtained from the experimentally measured repetition frequency (6.3 GHz) and total cavity length. The temperature induced differential index provided is a typical value for AlGaAs-based lasers [37]. The parameters for the active layer (n'_N , g' , N_{tr} , $\partial_T N_{\text{tr}}$) are determined from a calculation of the sub-band structure of the quantum well using an 8-band $\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{p}$ method and a subsequent determination of the complex-valued dielectric function due to the presence of excess carriers [38]. The model accounts for transition-broadening (using a sech broadening function [39] with a broadening of $\Delta E = \hbar/\tau_{\text{intra}} = 10$ meV [40]) and band-gap renormalization [41]. Figure 5 shows the modal gain against carrier density as obtained from the microscopic model and the fit above transparency based on equation (7). In this study, the transparency carrier density is slightly reduced from the fitted value of $3.2 \cdot 10^{24} \text{ m}^{-3}$ to $2.7 \cdot 10^{24} \text{ m}^{-3}$ to achieve a better agreement between the measured and calculated threshold currents, as shown in figure 6. Although the flat band conditions

assumed in the microscopic model are valid for the region above transparency, they do not apply to the absorber section. However, in the absence of detailed knowledge, the gain parameters derived above transparency are also used for the absorber section. The gain clamping density N_0 is assigned a value corresponding to the typical unintended doping density of the nominally undoped active region. It is much smaller than the carrier density generated in the absorber section during the passage of an optical pulse, which approaches the transparency carrier density. The gain compression factor is calculated as $\epsilon_g = \Gamma\epsilon$, where the nonlinear gain coefficient $\epsilon = 10^{-23} \text{ m}^3$ is taken from [42], and Γ is the confinement factor in the active region. This modification with Γ arises from a differing definition of the photon density $|u^\pm|^2$. Consequently, in equation (14), modal gain is used instead of material gain, as in [42]. The background absorption α_0 , due to doping of the layers and scattering loss at the ridge, is adjusted to fit the slope of the power–current characteristics. The cross–section for free–carrier absorption is determined as $f_N = \Gamma\sigma_N n_{AZ}/\bar{n}$, with $\sigma_N = 1.6 \cdot 10^{-21}$ (typical value for AlGaAs–based lasers) and $n_{AZ} = 3.61$. The parameters for two–photon absorption and the Kerr effect, weighted by the profile of the vertical waveguide mode, are obtained from [43] and [44] as described in [19]. The recombination parameters are typical values for AlGaAs–based lasers [35]. The hole mobility is obtained from [45]. The energy gap is given the value of the photon energy. The effective density of states are derived by fitting the dependence of quasi–Fermi potentials on the carrier density calculated with the microscopic model, as described in [38].

Regarding the temperature dependence of the parameters we refer to [20]. The reference temperature of the parameters is set equal to the heat sink temperature $T_{HS} = 300 \text{ K}$. The geometric parameters of the cavity are taken from table 1.

Figure 5. Gain parameter fitting: microscopic model (blue solid curve), fit of N_{tr} and g' (orange dashed curve), adjustment of N_{tr} used in the simulation (green dotted curve).

The electro–optical and thermal models are iterated as follows: An initial simulation is conducted under isothermal conditions for a duration of 3 ns. The time–averaged heat sources are then calculated, and the temperature–dependent parameters are updated accordingly. This is followed by three consecutive iterations to achieve a stable thermal state. Each iteration lasts 3 ns, 3 ns, and 10 ns, respectively, along with thermal

Table 2. Simulation parameters

parameter	symbol	value	unit
reference wavelength	λ	$820 \cdot 10^{-9}$	m
reference effective phase index	\bar{n}	3.359	
effective group index	n_g	3.975	
effective index step in RW sections	Δn_{eff}	$3 \cdot 10^{-3}$	
temperature induced differential effective index	n'_{T}	$2.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$	K^{-1}
confinement factor in active region	Γ	$1.46 \cdot 10^{-2}$	
total thickness of active region	d	$12 \cdot 10^{-9}$ m	
carrier density induced differential effective index	n'_{N}	$2.21 \cdot 10^{-31}$	m^3
gain prefactor	g'	5000	m^{-1}
transparency carrier density	N_{tr}	$2.7 \cdot 10^{24}$	m^{-3}
change of transparency carrier density with temperature	$\partial_{\text{T}} N_{\text{tr}}$	$3.54 \cdot 10^{22}$	$\text{m}^{-3} \text{K}^{-1}$
gain clamping carrier density	N_0	$2 \cdot 10^{22}$	m^{-3}
gain compression factor	ϵ_g	$1.46 \cdot 10^{-25}$	m^3
background absorption	α_0	110	m^{-1}
cross section of free carrier absorption	f_{N}	$2.51 \cdot 10^{-23}$	m^2
cross section of two-photon absorption	$f_{2\text{P}}$	$1.51 \cdot 10^{-23}$	m^2
Kerr effect	$n'_{2\text{P}}$	$-1.098 \cdot 10^{-30}$	m^3
inverse SRH recombination life time	A		
gain sections		10^8	s^{-1}
saturable absorber section		10^{10}	s^{-1}
radiative recombination parameter	B	10^{-16}	$\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$
Auger recombination parameter	C	$4 \cdot 10^{-42}$	$\text{m}^6 \text{s}^{-1}$
hole mobility in active layer	μ_p	$1.21 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$\text{m}^2 (\text{Vs})^{-1}$
energy gap	E_g	1.51	eV
conduction band effective density of states	N_c	$1.41 \cdot 10^{24}$	m^{-3}
valence band effective density of states	N_v	$1.24 \cdot 10^{25}$	m^{-3}

calculations and parameter updates. The entire iterative calculation spans a temporal scale of 19 ns, and yields stable results for a single simulation point (for a given U_0). The spatial and temporal resolutions for the computation are defined by the lateral and longitudinal mesh steps, $\Delta x = 0.2 \mu\text{m}$ and $\Delta z = 5 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. The temporal step Δt is determined by the group velocity $\Delta t = \Delta z / v_g$. The simulation was run on an Intel Xeon Gold 6154 CPU, utilizing 70 cores for parallel processing. It took approximately 5 hours to complete a single data point. The results presented in the next section are based on the data obtained from the final 10 ns of the last iteration.

4. Simulation results

In this section, we present the simulation results from two perspectives. First, we examine the optical performance, focusing on the characteristics of the emitted light and their correlation with experimental measurements. Second, we delve into the laser cavity, exploring the intra-cavity dynamics to provide insights into the behavior of tapered MLDLs.

4.1. Electro-optical performance

In the simulation, an optical pulse train is generated through passive ML, as in the experiment. Figure 6 presents the measured and simulated power-current characteristics of the device in passive ML, showing data for both increasing and decreasing bias in the gain sections. A bistability phenomenon, evident in both measurement and simulation, is observed between the lasing and non-lasing states, resulting in an abrupt turn-on at threshold. When decreasing the current, the laser turns off at a lower current than it turns on with increasing current, indicating hysteresis in the MLDL. This behavior can be attributed to the action of the saturable absorber [46]. Note that the turn-on or turn-off of the laser is always accompanied by a corresponding drop or rise in temperature. In the simulation, this temperature change translates into adjustments of temperature-dependent parameters in the electro-optical model. Since the thermal model is solved after each electro-optical iteration, representing a time-averaged thermal distribution, the parameters cannot be adapted in real time. Therefore, a small change in the voltage U_0 around the threshold results in a large jump in the current, as shown in the upwards simulated curve in figure 6 (right). For comparison, figure 6 also shows power-current curves for the device operating in CW mode. In the measurement, all three sections were shorted and driven by a single current source. In the simulation, the saturable absorber section was modeled identically to the RW gain section and forward biased at U_0 . The smoother turn-on transition around the threshold observed in the simulation, which closely resembles the measurement results, suggests that heat accumulation prior to laser turn-on, and its subsequent drop after turn-on, are significantly more pronounced in ML operation. Since in the experimental measurement the gain sections are driven with a current source and the delayed thermal behavior does not exist in real devices, the measured characteristics exhibit much less hysteresis. Nevertheless, there is still a notable resemblance between the simulated and measured power-current curves concerning the threshold and the average optical power achieved.

Figure 6. Measured (left) and simulated (right) averaged optical power versus increasing (blue, green) and decreasing (orange) gain current in ML and CW operation. In the right side figure, each bullet represents a simulation point, and the lines connecting the bullets serve as a guide to the eyes.

Simulated and measured optical and RF power spectra for a gain current of 3.3 A (measurement) and 3.5 A (simulation), respectively, corresponding to an average power of 0.8 W are presented in figure 7. The RF power spectrum reveals a fundamental repetition rate of 6.3 GHz both in experiment and simulation. The fact that the simulated RF power spectrum is not as finely resolved as the measured one (Rohde & Schwarz FSW50, resolution bandwidth: 100 kHz, video bandwidth: 100 kHz, measuring time: 300 ms) is due to the short data recording time (10 ns) for the discrete Fourier transform. It can be observed in figure 9 that the generated pulse train exhibits some amplitude jitter, likely caused by residual Q-switching [47]. This is evidenced by the small peaks around the fundamental repetition frequency and its harmonics in the measured RF power spectrum (also visible in figure 3). With a sufficiently long simulation recording time, the RF power spectrum would reveal finer details. At the same time, more precise estimations of both amplitude and timing jitter could be directly calculated from the pulse train, as is typically achieved in experiments using the RF power spectrum [48]. The simulated optical spectrum consists of many individual spectral peaks so that the area enclosed by the envelope and the wavelength axis appears to be filled. The difference in the peak wavelengths of the optical spectrum between measurement and simulation (831 nm vs. 822 nm) results from the fact that the simulation was done for a reference wavelength of $\lambda = 820$ nm but the later fabricated devices emitted at 830 nm. Although the spectral widths are comparable, the spectral background in the simulation is much smaller which is probably due to shortcomings of the Lorentzian spectral model used for gain and absorption.

Figure 7. Measured RF power spectrum (upper left), measured optical power spectrum (upper right), simulated RF power spectrum (lower left), and simulated optical power spectrum (lower right) at an average power of 0.8 W.

Figure 8 shows the FWHM width of the pulses, averaged from the width of each

Figure 8. Simulated pulse width versus gain current (left): average FWHM pulse width over 10 ns (blue) and pulse width from Gaussian fit of ACF (orange) and pulse peak power versus gain current (right): average peak power over 10 ns (blue) and peak power calculated from Gaussian fit of ACF (orange).

Figure 9. Output pulse trains for the last 10 ns in the simulation at a gain current of 3.5 A (upper left) and 4.5 A (lower left), exemplary single pulses from each pulse train (upper right), and the ACF traces (lower right, solid lines) of each pulse train with their corresponding Gaussian fit curves (lower right, dotted lines).

single pulse generated over the last 10 ns in the simulation, alongside the calculated pulse width obtained by fitting a Gaussian curve to the ACF trace of the 10 ns pulse train. The fitted pulse width is notably shorter than the averaged pulse width for gain currents below 4.4 A. Nevertheless, both widths increase in tandem with the gain current, maintaining a difference of approximately 0.4 ps until the behavior changes. Beyond 4.5 A, the fitted curve experiences a sharp increase, while the averaged pulse width drops with fluctuation. The corresponding peak power, as shown in figure 8 (right), exhibits a similar behavior. Below 4.4 A, the peak power calculated from the

Gaussian fit, slightly larger, increases gradually alongside the averaged peak power, maintaining a constant difference of 10 W. Around 4.4 A, the averaged curve jumps from 90 W to 100 W, while the fitted curve drops from 100 W to 70 W.

This peculiar behavior, which is similarly reflected in the experimental data in figure 2, can only be understood by closely examining the temporal pulse traces. Therefore, we select two simulation points as examples: gain currents of 3.5 A (average power of 0.8 W) and 4.5 A (average power of 1.7 W), representing the two distinct sections in the pulse width curves. The complete 10 ns pulse trains for both gain currents are presented in figure 9, along with examples of single pulses and the ACF of the corresponding pulse traces. While both pulse trains show subtle differences in amplitude modulation, the closer examination of individual pulses reveals significant differences in pulse shapes between these two sample points. At 3.5 A, a single peak is observed, while at 4.5 A, the pulse has two peaks. Consequently, the resulting ACFs also differ from each other. The ACF at 3.5 A has a Gaussian-like shape, whereas the ACF at 4.5 A shows a dominant coherent peak. Notably, pulses below 4.4 A consistently exhibit a single peak akin to those observed at 3.5 A, while pulses above 4.4 A display multiple peaks similar to those seen at 4.5 A. This insight clarifies the discrepancy observed in figure 8 between the averaged and fitted pulse widths and peak powers, and helps to improve the understanding of the experimental observations in figure 2.

Figure 10. Pulse trains (left column) and single pulses (right column) simulated with different A parameters at a gain current of 3.5 A.

Figure 10 shows pulse trains along with an example of a single pulse from each train for three different A parameters, all at a gain current of 3.5 A. Each pulse train shows an amplitude jitter, potentially attributable to residual Q-switching, as discussed earlier. Additionally, the averaged pulse width, calculated by averaging the FWHM of all individual pulses over this 10 ns interval, decreases with increasing A parameter, corresponding to a shorter carrier lifetime in the absorber region. This observation aligns with our experimental results reported in [8], where the pulse width, calculated from the ACF, decreases with increasing reverse bias voltage on the absorber section. For $A = 10^{11} s^{-1}$, a steep leading edge of the pulse is observed, a phenomenon attributed to the shorter carrier lifetime, which emulates the effect of a fast saturable absorber. In the case where $A = 10^8 s^{-1}$, the carrier lifetime in the absorber region is equal to that in the gain region. This corresponds to the experimental scenario in which mode locking could still be observed even when no external bias is applied to the absorber section. Nevertheless, for demonstration purposes, we primarily focus on presenting the results for $A = 10^{10} s^{-1}$.

4.2. Intra-cavity characteristics

Figure 11. Pseudo-color mappings of the intra-cavity distributions of time averaged field intensity (top row), carrier density (middle row) and temperature (bottom row) for both CW (left column) and ML (right column) operation at a gain current of 3.5 A. The dashed lines denote the separation between the gain and saturable absorber sections, as well as the outline of the electrical contact on the TP region.

Figure 11 presents characteristics inside the laser cavity averaged over a duration

of 10 ns for a gain current of 3.5 A in both CW and ML operations. In both cases, the supplied power is about 5.5 W, the average output power are 1.3 W and 0.8 W, respectively (according to figure 6). Figure 11 includes three sets of figures showing the distributions of total optical field intensity $(\hbar\omega c/n_g)\langle|u^+(x, z, t)|^2 + |u^-(x, z, t)|^2\rangle$, carrier density $\langle N(x, z, t)\rangle$, and temperature $T(x, y_a, z)$ at the position y_a with the active layer.

Due to the asymmetric facet coating, the maximum field intensity in the CW case occurs at the transition region from the RW gain section to the TP gain section. This is where the reflected light from the front facet, propagating through the cavity and experiencing continuous gain, begins to expand laterally into the TP region, and then the intensity increases again along the longitudinal direction in the TP gain region towards the front facet. Meanwhile, in the ML configuration, the maximum intensity is observed at the transition region from the RW gain section to the saturable absorber section. Similar to the CW case, the intensity experiences a drop at the transition from the RW into the TP gain section, followed by a gradual increase towards the front facet. The intensity distribution in the TP gain section is similar to the CW scenario. The observed periodic pattern is mainly an artifact resulting from insufficient temporal averaging.

The carrier density plots reveal a noticeable carrier accumulation outside the RW and TP electrical contact areas in both CW and ML cases. The carriers outside the contact regions of the gain sections originate partially from carrier diffusion and partially from optical generation. In particular, around the interface between the RW and TP gain sections, an increased concentration of optically generated charge carriers is observed, primarily due to the absorption of the outwardly radiated optical field in this region. This phenomenon is visualized in figure 12, where the back-propagating light interacts strongly with the contact edges. Within the TP section, carrier accumulation is more pronounced near the contact edges compared to the inner region. This occurs because, as the forward-propagating light expands, the lowers optical intensity towards the edges results in reduced stimulated recombination. In the ML case, since longitudinal carrier diffusion is not accounted for in the saturable absorber section, an unphysical sharp transition in carrier density is observed between the RW absorber and gain sections. Nevertheless, carrier accumulation still occurs in this region due to optical generation.

The mappings of the time-averaged temperature distribution in both CW and ML cases indicate significant heat accumulation in the TP gain section, particularly near the output facet. This phenomenon results from the combined effects of increased optical intensity near the front facet, which enhances absorption-induced heating, and inadequate lateral heat spreading. This lateral-longitudinal temperature distribution subsequently affects the refractive index, resulting in the so-called thermal lensing effect [30], which causes a narrowing of the optical field. In the ML scenario, the laser is noticeably ‘hotter’ at the front facet compared to the CW case, reflecting only the time-averaged effect. In pulsed operation, the pulse intensity is much higher than in the CW case, leading to greater transient local heating. However, this thermal dynamic is not accounted for in the simulation.

Figure 12. Pseudo-color snapshots of the distribution of the field intensity at different stages of the round trip of a pulse within the cavity (left column) and corresponding longitudinal profiles of the optical power with zoomed insets (right column). The dashed lines denote the separation between the gain and saturable absorber sections, as well as the outline of the RW ridge and TP region.

Furthermore, the simulation offers the opportunity to examine the pulse propagation inside the laser cavity. The left column of figure 12 shows snapshots of the field intensity distribution at various stages of a pulse's round trip within the cavity at a gain current of 3.5 A. These stages include: just after reflection at the front facet (0 ps), leaving the TP gain section (44 ps), leaving the RW gain section (73 ps), after reflection at the rear facet in the saturable absorber section (80 ps), upon entering the TP gain section (112 ps), and just before the transmission through the front facet (156 ps). The corresponding evolutions of the pulse shape during a round

trip are shown in the right column of figure 12. The reflected pulse initially gradually increases in intensity as it travels backward through the TP gain section. During the backward propagation, the electrically induced lateral waveguiding in the TP region becomes progressively narrower, causing the optical field to interact more with the contact edges. This interaction results in light emitting outside the TP gain region. Especially at the transition from TP gain to RW gain, the leaking radiation becomes more pronounced, as evident in the carrier density distribution outside the p-contacts in figure 11, resulting in a decrement in pulse intensity. Additionally, the pulse is notably deformed due to longitudinal spatial hole burning in the amplifying RW gain section, where the leading edge of the pulse experiences greater amplification than the trailing edge. Upon entering the saturable absorber section, the pulse intensity again reduces due to the simulated absorbing effect modeled by the increased A parameter. During the forward propagation in the gain sections, the interaction with contact edges is much less prominent compared to backward propagation. Instead, a continuous increase in the pulse intensity, particularly in the TP region, is observed, resulting in a pulse with high peak power.

5. Summary and outlook

We adapted a general-purpose program, designed for simulation of the spatio-temporal behavior of diode lasers, to specifically model a passively mode-locked tapered laser. The program numerically solves traveling wave equations in the lateral-longitudinal plane, as well as equations governing current flow in the vertical-lateral plane, lateral carrier diffusion in the active layer, and self-heating in the vertical-lateral plane. The theoretical model underlying the simulation tool accounts for several non-linear effects, such as lateral and longitudinal spatial hole-burning, gain compression, two-photon absorption, and the Kerr effect.

Consistent with experimental observations, the three-section TP laser spontaneously enters a passive ML state when a constant forward bias is applied to the gain section. Simulated results demonstrate generation of single-peaked pulses with a duration of approximately 2 ps and peak power exceeding 80 W across a broad range of gain currents, closely resembling experimental findings.

For a fixed gain current, mode locking was observed for a large range of the recombination parameter A which mainly determines the carrier lifetime in the absorber section. Independently of the carrier lifetime, we also observed a modulation of the pulse amplitudes, which can be attributed to residual Q-switching, a phenomenon that is also visible in the measured RF spectra. Furthermore, the simulation provided valuable insights into the intra-cavity distribution of optical fields, carrier density, and temperature, as well as the dynamics of pulses within the laser cavity. The simulations revealed an overheating of the tapered section, which was more pronounced in ML than in CW operation. Proper mounting of the ML tapered laser is therefore essential to ensure adequate heat dissipation.

The simulation tool will be further utilized to explore the spatial lateral profiles of the pulse train and to optimize the laser structure for improved beam quality. Future modeling efforts will aim to more comprehensively incorporate dispersion effects, such as group velocity dispersion and gain dispersion. Additionally, we plan to refine the description of saturable absorber to improve the overall accuracy and predictive capability of our model. These advancements will contribute to a deeper understanding of tapered MLDL dynamics and support the design of more efficient and high-performance laser devices.

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